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The Development of Relations between the Slovak and the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences until 1970¹

ADAM HUDEK

Abstract: The study analyses the development of the mutual relationship between the Slovak and Czechoslovak academies of sciences from the early 1950s to the beginning of the normalisation regime. It focuses on three key periods: the founding period of both institutions, the centralising tendencies of the early 1960s and the attempt at fundamental reform during the liberalising period of the Prague Spring. These processes are examined from the perspective of the Slovak Academy, as it was this institution that was influenced by the changes described here, and its representatives provided the impulses to redefine the existing situation.

Keywords: Slovak Academy of Sciences, Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences, centralisation, science policy

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Introduction

The definition and development of the relationship between the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences (hereafter: CSAS) and the Slovak Academy of Sciences (hereafter: SAS) were one of the formative organisational elements of Czechoslovak science in the second half of the 20th century. This relationship was determined not only by plans and contemporary visions of effective and productive scientific research. The cooperation between the two, at least officially, leading scientific research institutions in Czechoslovakia often came under the scrutiny of key communist party and government officials. This meant that the

¹ This study is part of a project funded by the the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101038067. The research presented in this study was carried out within the framework of the VEGA grant 2/0099/20 "University research in the context of constitutional and political changes in Slovakia in the period 1918–1968", which is being implemented at the Institute of History, Slovak Academy of Sciences.

mutual position of the two academies mirrored the political and legal changes in the state and upheavals that shaped society as a whole.

This study examines the relationship between the CSAS and the SAS from their establishment to the early 1970s. In contrast to the stability of the so-called normalisation period that followed, the relationship between the two institutions underwent several significant changes during this time. Emphasis is placed on three key periods. The first is the early 1950s, when the two academies were founded and it was necessary to define their mutual status and forms of cooperation. This process began even before the establishment of the SAS and included high-level political negotiations. The second period examined herein is the turn of the 1950s and 1960s, when the desire for effective scientific work led the highest party bodies to pass a decision stripping the Slovak Academy of its autonomous status and incorporating it directly into the CSAS.

The changes implemented from 1960 to 1963 represented a fundamental attempt to modify the structure of science and research in the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic. In the late 1960s, however, the political and economic situation and the mood in society began to change. These developments largely contradicted the foundations on which science and research institutions had been restructured in the early 1960s. As a result, there was a call for radical changes in the relations between the CSAS and the SAS, which were eventually introduced in 1968 especially in Slovakia. The reform period of the Prague Spring is therefore the third and last period of interest in this study.

The study approaches the topic primarily from the Slovak perspective. The reason for this is that the developments described here largely influenced the functioning and position of the Slovak Academy. It was also the representatives of this institution who, in 1968–1969, proposed fundamental changes in the legal status of the CSAS and SAS.

This study is partly based on the research and texts prepared by the author for publications on the history of the Slovak Academy of Sciences² and the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences.³ The intention of the text is thus to use existing materials to analyse a longer time frame than has been explored by

2 HUDEK, Adam. Slovenská akadémia vied a umení v rokoch 1945–1952. Prerod SAVU do Slovenskej akadémie vied. In KOVÁČ, Dušan (ed.). *Dejiny Slovenskej akadémie vied*. Bratislava: VEDA, 2014, pp. 69–86; IDEM. Slovenská akadémia vied v “obrodnom procese” 1968–1969. In *Ibid.*, pp. 145–166 (hereafter: HUDEK, A. *Slovenská akadémia vied v “obrodnom procese”*); HUDEK, Adam, KLAČKA, Jozef. Slovenská akadémia vied v zložitých podmienkach komunistickej totality a jej krízy (1953–1967). In *Ibid.*, pp. 107–142 (hereafter: HUDEK, A., KLAČKA, J. *Slovenská akadémia vied v zložitých podmienkach*).

3 HUDEK, Adam. ČSAV a SAV 1952–1956. In FRANC, Martin, DVOŘÁČKOVÁ Věra et al. *Dějiny Československé akademie věd. I. 1952–1962*. Praha: Academia – Masarykův ústav a Archiv AV ČR, 2019, pp. 278–291; IDEM. ČSAV a SAV 1957–1962. In *Ibid.*, pp. 394–407.

previous studies. The primary aim is to overcome the limited chronological timelines in which the topic is presented in the above-mentioned works. The objective is to present a broader, long-term overview essential for a profound understanding of the development of the CSAS and the SAS. In this way, the developmental continuities and discontinuities in the topic will become more apparent. An additional important ambition of this study is to present the outcomes of the research into the relationship between the two academies to an international audience. The history of the CSAS as well as the SAS are so far available only in Czech and Slovak.

Defining Relationships in the 1950s

The idea to centralise Czechoslovak science and research in the Academy of Sciences emerged almost immediately after the end of the Second World War. The new Czechoslovak government opened a debate on the potential establishment of the CSAS in 1946, sending its proposal to the main scientific institutions in the Czechoslovak Republic. These included the Slovak Academy of Sciences and Arts (hereafter: SAVU), founded in 1942 and again in early 1946.⁴ Unlike universities, this institution was to be directly involved in the government plan, as it was to become part of the CSAS. Most of the institutions approached rejected the plan to establish a central institution. In the case of the SAVU, however, it was not entirely clear-cut, and the reactions of its representatives also reflected the dilemmas that defined the development of relations between the Czechoslovak and Slovak academies in the later period.

In 1946, the official administrator of the SAVU, Mikuláš Bakoš, agreed in principle to the establishment of the CSAS. He justified this by the need for science planning and mutual information about ongoing research. Moreover, if Slovak science was to progress and especially expand its scope to encompass technical and natural disciplines, the help and support of the incomparably more developed Czech academic community were inevitable. On the other hand, the representatives of the SAVU were determined to preserve the autonomous status of Slovak science and research. They agreed to the establishment of a statewide⁵ academy only on condition that it would comprise separate Czech and Slovak sections and that Slovakia would be represented equally in its leadership: “In this way, the interests of Slovak science would be secured

4 In 1946, it was on a “people’s democratic basis” in order to remove its wartime, “clerofascist” origin.

5 The term “statewide” is used herein to refer to the whole of Czechoslovakia, while “national” is deemed to be construed as “Slovak”.

even with the statewide organisation of scientific work and the coordination of scientific research in Slovakia in proportion to the rest of the Republic.”⁶ The plan that the future CSAS would represent “the interests of both Czech and Slovak science in the field of international scientific cooperation as the only central representative body of the Czechoslovak Republic of this kind”⁷ was what aroused the greatest criticism. In 1946, due to the opposition of the institutions concerned, the centralisation programme could not be pushed through. However, it foreshadowed the future direction of the organisation of science and research in Czechoslovakia, mainly because the Communists were among its great supporters.

The plan to establish the CSAS had come about almost immediately after the Communists’ seizure of power in 1948.⁸ This time, however, it no longer took the form of a proposal but of a directive order. No one had asked the SAVU representatives for their opinion. As presented at the IX Congress of the Communist Party of Slovakia (CPS) on 24–27 May 1950 by its General Secretary, Stefan Bašťovanský, “There is one working class, and that is also how the activities of the SAVU should be approached: As the activities of the unified Czechoslovak Academy, even though it has not yet been formally established.”⁹ Of course, for the building up of the two new academies, such simplistic ideological slogans could not suffice. They did, however, roughly define the ideas of their mutual status.

At the outset, the question must be answered as to why, during the struggle against Slovak “bourgeois nationalism”, the party leadership agreed to establish the Slovak Academy of Sciences, especially when the SAVU was severely criticised in 1952 for serious “ideological shortcomings in its work” that prevented it from becoming a “*socialist-type academy*”.¹⁰ The main reason to establish the new autonomous academy was the conviction that the problems

6 Centre of Operations of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Archive of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava (hereafter: A SAS), Coll. SAVU, box 8, The Question of the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences, opinion of the Slovak scientific community, 26 February 1947.

7 Ibid., Analysis of the theoretical possibilities that arise to resolve the question of the establishment of the CSAS.

8 For detailed information, see: JAREŠ, Jakub, FRANC, Martin et al. *Mezi konkurencí a spoluprací. Univerzita Karlova a Československá akademie věd 1945–1969*. Praha: Karolinum, 2018, pp. 169–189.

9 Cited from: KLAČKA, Jozef. Prerastanie SAVU do SAV. In PÖSS, Ondrej (ed.). *Z dejín vied a techniky na Slovensku*. XVI. *Slovenská akadémia vied a umení*. Bratislava: Historický ústav SAV, 1994, p. 44.

10 Slovak National Archives, Bratislava (hereafter: SNA), Coll. Central Committee of the Communist Party of Slovakia (hereafter: CC CPS), box 822, Meetings of the Presidium of the CC CPS August–September 1952, Bratislava, Report on preparations for the implementation of the Law on the CSAS.

in Czech-Slovak relations should be resolved by raising Slovakia's economy to the level of the Czech lands. The anticipated rapid modernisation required a specific approach, which was to be provided, among other things, by the SAS. In other words, it was necessary "to create the Slovak Academy of Sciences in addition to the statewide academy because Slovak science has to cope with issues related to the turbulent economic and cultural development of Slovakia."¹¹ What probably also played a role was the fact that the abolition of the Slovak Academy of Arts and Sciences without providing a replacement would undoubtedly provoke a wave of resentment in the Slovak academic and intellectual community, which in previous years had devoted considerable energy to the preservation and further development of the Slovak Academy.¹²

The concept of the SAS as an institution dealing with "specific issues of Slovak development" quite concretely determined its planned form. According to the original plans, it was to be focused on practical, "local" research problems and those social sciences which existed within the SAVU. Institutes of basic research in the field of natural and technical sciences were to function only within the statewide CSAS. The activities of the Slovak members of the Governmental Commission for the Establishment of the CSAS were also carried out in this direction. The historian and high-ranking party official, Miloš Gosiorovský, the virologist Dionýz Blaškovič and the physicist Dionýz Ilkovič proposed that a number of top scientific institutes based in Slovakia should become part of the CSAS and not the SAS.¹³ These proposals had pragmatic reasons. Slovakia's top scientific institutions had a much better prospect of development within the statewide CSAS than in the "regional" SAS, about whose form there were only vague ideas in mid-1952.

This concept, however, also had strong opponents. They were led by Ján Gonda, rector of the Slovak Technical University and chairman of the SAVU Administration, who persistently warned the Slovak Authorised Office for Education, Sciences and Arts that the proposals for the future relationship between the CSAS and the SAS were highly detrimental to the development of Slovak science and research: "In order to ensure academic life in Slovakia, it is necessary to coordinate the whole of it without exceptions [underlined in

11 ŠTOLL, Ladislav. Zpráva o činnosti vládní komise pro přípravu ČSAV. *Věstník ČSAV*, 1953, Vol. 62, No. 1–2, p. 17.

12 For similar reasons, *Matica Slovenská* [The Slovak Matica] was also preserved, although in a reduced form.

13 These were the Office of Virology of the Slovak Central Institute of Biology, the observatory at Skalnaté Pleso in the High Tatras, and the Geophysical Laboratory in Hurbanovo. See: Masaryk Institute and Archives of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Coll. Governmental Commission for the Establishment of the CSAS, box 1, Minutes of the Plenary Meeting of the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences, 26 and 27 May 1952.

the original text]. It is therefore not possible to take the best institutes out of Slovak cooperation, assign them directly to the CSAS and leave only the rest for the Slovak Academy.¹⁴ J. Gonda demanded that all scientific institutes in Slovakia should be placed under the Slovak Academy of Sciences, with cooperation with the CSAS consisting only of coordination in research planning. This proposal assumed the existence of two equal national academies, which, however, was not realistic given the existing plans for the organisation of science and research in Czechoslovakia.

In August 1952, the Presidium of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Slovakia (CC CPS) approved the establishment of the Board of Commissioners' Commission for the Establishment of the Slovak Academy of Sciences.¹⁵ Its members were renowned Slovak scientists, and it was headed by Ondrej Pavlík, a high-ranking party official, who was assumed to become the president of the SAS. The founding of the commission indicated that the leadership of the CPS and the Office for Education were beginning to take an interest in the organisation of the future Slovak academy and were no longer leaving all the activity to the Government Commission for the Establishment of the CSAS and other central authorities. Pavlík defined the fundamental goals of his commission. He did not question the fact that the CSAS would be the highest academic organisation in the state and that without its active help the SAS would not be able to function.¹⁶ However, he argued that it was unacceptable not to include in the SAS the existing basic research institutes in Slovakia.¹⁷

In October 1952, talks took place in Bratislava by members of the Government Commission for the Establishment of the CSAS.¹⁸ Some of the original proposals concerning the division of competencies were revised. The overall scope of activity of the SAS and the list of its scientific institutes were approved by the CC CPS on 1 November 1952, two days after the adoption of the law on the CSAS, and subsequently by the Board of Commissioners. As the Commission for the Establishment of the SAS stated, "the CSAS comrades have fully adopted the principle that the relationship between the CSAS and the SAS should be regulated also as far as the division of scientific institutes is

14 A SAS, Coll. Ján Gonda, box 3, Establishment of the SAS.

15 HUDEK, Adam, KLAČKA, Jozef. Vznik Slovenskej akadémie vied. In KOVÁČ, Dušan (ed.). *Dejiny Slovenskej akadémie vied*. Bratislava: VEDA, 2014, p. 95.

16 A SAS, Coll. Executive Bodies of the SAS (hereafter: RO SAV), box 1, Minutes of the First Session of the Commission of the Board of Commissioners for the Establishment of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, 8 October 1952.

17 Ibid.

18 Including its chairman, Ladislav Štoll.

concerned in a manner analogous to that in the USSR.¹⁹ This was only a vague statement that could mean many things. Further details were brought by meetings held in December 1952 in the office of Deputy Prime Minister Zdeněk Fierlinger. Among other things, it was agreed that the SAS would carry out basic scientific research in all academic disciplines.²⁰

Although the negotiations on the mutual relationship between the CSAS and the SAS were rather long and complicated, the basic legal documents of both academies mention this aspect only very briefly. The Act on the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences merely states that the CSAS follows the progressive traditions of Czech and Slovak science.²¹ The Act on the Slovak Academy of Sciences acknowledges the obligation of the Slovak Academy to carry out its tasks “in purposeful coordination [...] with the activities of the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences as the supreme academic institution of the Czechoslovak Republic.”²² The only area in which the subordination of the Slovak Academy of Sciences was explicitly, and in greater detail formulated, were international relations.

In the speeches delivered at the inaugurations of the two academies, promises were made of mutual cooperation and all-round assistance of “advanced Czech science to young, often novice Slovak science.”²³ The reality of the mutual relations, however, was much more prosaic. The presidium of the Czechoslovak Academy had almost no tools with which to influence the internal development of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, and did not even try to do so. It may have been affected by the mutual antagonism between the President of the CSAS, Zdeněk Nejedlý, and the President of the SAS, O. Pavlík. František Šorm, the influential Secretary General of the CSAS, was quite contemptuous towards the SAS and openly stated that it did not need institutes of basic research.²⁴ That certainly did not make him a popular figure in the Slovak academic community.

19 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 1, Minutes of Meeting the Commission of the Board of Commissioners for the Establishment of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, 1 November 1952.

20 *Ibid.*, box 1. Minutes of the meeting on the Slovak Academy of Sciences held on 19 December 1952 in the office of Deputy Prime Minister, Zdeněk Fierlinger.

21 Act No. 52/1952 Sb. On the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences. Online: <<http://www.zakonyprolidi.cz/cs/1952-52#p1>> [Accessed 29 October 2022].

22 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 2, Act on the Establishment of the SAS, Explanatory Report.

23 Stenographic report on the course of the 6th and 7th meetings of the Slovak National Council of 16 June 1955 in Bratislava, Report of the President of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Academician Ondrej Pavlík, on the first two years of activity and development of the Slovak Academy of Sciences. Online: <<http://www.psp.cz/eknih/1954snr/stenprot/006schuz/s006002.htm>> [Accessed 29 October 2022].

24 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 4, 5th General Assembly of the SAS, 18–19 March 1955, Speech of the Scientific Secretary of the CSAS, František Šorm.

A rule was followed, however, that scientists of the CSAS were appointed at the scientific sections and councils of the SAS, and vice versa. However, such nominees only rarely attended meetings held outside their institutes. Joint meetings of the representatives of the scientific sections of the SAS and the CSAS took on the form of mutual information exchanges rather than planning joint research projects. In 1955, František Šorm openly complained that, unlike Comenius University in Bratislava, the SAS did not send any of its young researchers to the CSAS, although it should have done so on the basis of the existing agreements.²⁵

Regarding the relationship between the CSAS and the SAS, many issues were unresolved and there were no clearly defined rules, rights and obligations. Disputes over competence, however, were rare and the practical application of only vaguely defined principles of cooperation evolved into a well-established system. The contacts between the two institutions which yielded scientific results functioned more along unofficial, personal lines. In the early 1950s, scientific cooperation went on mostly between individual scientists with similar scientific interests. In official terms, members of the academic elite in the leadership of strictly hierarchical academies decided on the methods and coordination of mutual cooperation.

Centrally organised scientific cooperation, not only between academies but between all science and research institutions in Czechoslovakia, only came at the beginning of 1956. The impetus for the changes came from the USSR, where Khrushchev's "new policy" began to embody a doctrine emphasising science's contribution to society's material development. The report by O. Pavlík to the Board of Commissioners in June 1955 already stated that "the stage of formal declarations of cooperation has already passed, and close cooperation has been adopted directly in planning and implementing scientific and research tasks".²⁶

The resolution of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia (hereafter: CC CPC) and the government of 22 February 1956, entitled "On the tasks of science in ensuring the development and raising the technical level of Czechoslovak industry", opened a new stage in Czechoslovak science. It defined a plan that primarily focused on the activities of the CSAS, but was also binding for the SAS. The Presidium of the Board

25 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 4, 5th General Assembly of the SAS, 18–19 March 1955, Speech of the Scientific Secretary of the CSAS, František Šorm.

26 Stenographic report on the course of the 6th and 7th meetings of the Slovak National Council of 16 June 1955 in Bratislava, Report of the President of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Academician Ondrej Pavlík, on the first two years of activity and development of the Slovak Academy of Sciences. Online: <<http://www.psp.cz/eknih/1954snr/stenprot/006schuz/s006002.htm>> [Accessed 10 October 2022].

of Commissioners adopted a number of resolutions, the most specific of which established 12 commissions to coordinate work in particular scientific areas.²⁷ Their task was to assess the scientific research plans of the institutes, and from them to determine the tasks of key importance. These were to be incorporated in the State Plan of Key Scientific Research Work for 1958–1960, prepared by the CSAS. The SAS was to become much more involved in the state plan of development of the national economy.²⁸ The changes increased the powers of the SAS in the management of science in Slovakia, but at the same time subordinated it more closely and precisely to the coordinating function of the CSAS.

Centralisation Efforts

At the turn of the 1950s and 1960s, this policy led to a decision by the highest party bodies to strip the Slovak Academy of its autonomous status and incorporate it directly into the CSAS.

The aim was to centralise scientific research in the state before entering the third Five-year Plan. This process was launched by a speech by the Czechoslovak President and First Secretary of the CC CPC, Antonín Novotný, at the party's Central Committee meeting on 23 September 1959. He began by criticising the shortcomings in the management of the work of the SAS: "Given its relation to the CSAS, statewide consideration was not always applied, and there was no uniform procedure in the management of scientific work and in providing for the education of academic staff." According to Novotný, there was a lack of coordination and efficiency. The solution could only be a unified science management and strengthening of the governing role of the CSAS throughout the territory of the republic.²⁹

Centralisation was presented as an appreciation of Slovak development in the last decade: "The rapid development of Slovak culture and science made it possible for Slovak scientific institutes not only to solve tasks of a specific national character, but also to participate far more intensively in solving tasks

27 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 665, Report on the implementation of the resolutions of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia and the Government of 22 February 1956 on the tasks of science in ensuring the development and raising the technical level of Czechoslovak industry by the Slovak Academy of Sciences.

28 The reality, however, was again a little less bright. In 1958, the SAS was the main investigator of 80% of the scheduled key scientific research tasks in Slovakia, while it participated in the implementation of the State Plan of Key Scientific Research Works for 1958–1960 with only 15% of its research capacity.

29 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 665, Measures resulting for the Slovak Academy of Sciences from the speech by comrade A. Novotný at the meeting of the CC CPC on 23–24 September 1959.

of statewide importance.³⁰ The entire process was then explained as a natural outcome of the continuously deepening cooperation between the CSAS and the Slovak Academy of Sciences.

At the end of February 1960, the highest party bodies adopted a resolution of the CC CPC “On the new arrangement of relations between the CSAS and the Slovak Academy of Sciences”. The fundamental change in the functioning of the SAS was thus brought about not by an official government regulation but by a party resolution. The proposal envisaged that the statewide academy would “manage the research at institutes located in Slovakia that are of extraordinary statewide importance.”³¹ In terms of improving the quality of academic staff, it was to ensure the internships of Slovak scientists at Czech scientific research institutes, as well as the support for Slovak scientific institutes by providing Czech experts.³² It was also (again) explicitly emphasised that the CSAS would be the sole representative of Czechoslovak science externally.

It was hardly to be expected that these proposals would not provoke a wave of disapproval in Slovakia, especially if they were presented in the typically insensitive style of A. Novotný. In the resolution of the Political Bureau of the CC CPC, the CSAS was portrayed as a Czech institution sending its staff to uplift the lagging Slovak academy, insinuating that Slovak academicians could only advance scientifically at Czech institutes. Similar claims supported existing prejudices of the Slovak academic community about Czech hegemonism, Prague-based centralism and contempt for Slovaks. Based on later statements made by some Slovak scientists in 1968, it can be assumed that this was exactly how a significant part of the SAS staff perceived the centralising activities in science and research.

However, in the early 1960s, during the ongoing struggle against bourgeois nationalism,³³ open criticism was still dangerous. Nevertheless, hidden expressions of disapproval were also cautiously admitted by the then President of the SAS, Andrej Sirácky.³⁴ He tried to reassure his colleagues with the prescient assertion that closer cooperation with the CSAS would benefit Slovak science.

30 Report presented by F. Šorm at the 11th General Assembly of the CSAS on 15–16 April 1960. See VLACH, Róbert. *Slovenská akadémia vied 1953–1967*. Brno: TISK, 1969, p. 29.

31 Institutes of the CSAS and the SAS with related activities were to have unified plans of scientific and research work.

32 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 665, Measures resulting for the Slovak Academy of Sciences from the speech by comrade A. Novotný at the meeting of the CC CPC on 23–24 September 1959.

33 Still in 1959, scientists from the Slovak Matica were accused of exhibiting bourgeois nationalism and given lengthy sentences.

34 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 4, Resolutions of the 14th General Assembly of the SAS, 30 December 1960.

This was expected to mainly concern physics and cybernetics, but the greatest benefit from the improved link eventually went to the social sciences.

The principles and measures defining the new relations between the academies came into force on 1 July 1960. On that date, the SAS became an “organic” part of the CSAS. The year 1961 was dedicated to preparing the new organisational statutes of the CSAS in a form that, among other things, reflected the new status of the SAS. A symbolic confirmation that the Slovak Academy had become part of the CSAS was the election of a new President of the Slovak Academy of Sciences on 7 December 1961, the virologist D. Blaškovič, one of the most prominent Slovak scientists, director of the successful CSAS Institute of Virology based in Bratislava, and one of the founding figures of both academies. The new President of the Slovak Academy of Sciences thus became a symbol of their strong link, probably the main reason he was appointed to this position.

Paradoxically, when he took office, a process of correction of the drastic centralisation plans had already begun. There were numerous reasons for this. The first was that the idea to make the entire decision-making process the sole competence of the CSAS Presidium proved unworkable in practice. On the other hand, the Presidium did not try too hard to control the SAS. In fact, there was no managing of the activities of the SAS other than requiring annual reports to be sent to Prague and regularly holding joint meetings of the governing bodies of the two academies. The representatives of the Slovak Academy tried to retain at least some executive powers that would not be subject to Prague’s approval. According to A. Sirácky, although the SAS leadership could not openly oppose decisions that were disadvantageous to the SAS, it was able to sabotage them by inaction.³⁵

An important reason for the change was that the government had lost interest in developments in the academies of sciences. The party leadership began to promote the view that it was beyond the power and capacity of the CSAS (and within it, the SAS) to overcome the lagging behind of Czechoslovak applied research and the practical use of its results.³⁶ After the establishment of the “State Commission for the Development and Coordination of Science and Technology”, the development of the CSAS was no longer seen as a priority.³⁷

35 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 8, Minutes of the 26th General Assembly of the SAS, 10 April 1968, Discussion paper by Andrej Sirácky.

36 MÍŠKOVÁ, Alena, BARVÍKOVÁ, Hana, ŠMIDÁK, Miroslav. *Československá akademie věd 1969–1972. Restaurace komunistické moci ve vědě*. Praha: Ústav pro soudobé dějiny AV ČR, 1998, p. 14 (hereafter: MÍŠKOVÁ, A., BARVÍKOVÁ, H., ŠMIDÁK, M. *Československá akademie věd*).

37 HUDEK, A, KLAČKA, J. *Slovenská akadémia vied v zložitých podmienkach*, p. 128.

This greatly facilitated the promotion of particularistic interests by the SAS. The fact that the merger of the academies was decided by a party resolution, while the legal norm was to be adopted later on the grounds of experience with the centralising measures, proved to be an advantage for the opponents of this process. It meant that the new law did not necessarily have to copy the original decision if it turned out that some of its stipulations did not work in practice.

Through a series of inconspicuous successive steps and agreements within the two academies, it was possible to ensure that the SAS did not dissolve into the CSAS and retained its status as the highest “national and regional scientific institution.” In 1968, the scientific secretary of the Slovak Academy, Miloš Gosiorovský, described the behind-the-scenes struggles to maintain the existence of the SAS as an autonomous institution. He portrayed them as a duel between the Slovak representatives of the SAS, and the representatives of the CC CPC³⁸ supported by František Šorm.³⁹ However, as Miroslav Šmidák, then head of the secretariat of the CSAS Presidium, wrote, the leadership of the CPC did not put up much resistance in the end: “It is worth noting that this gradual softening and then actually annulment of the resolution of the CC CPC on the relations between the CSAS and the SAS took place with the knowledge and tacit consent of the same party functionaries who had pushed it through less than two years earlier.”⁴⁰

The fact that the SAS formally retained its status as a national academy had concrete consequences. Its top representatives demanded that a special law on the SAS be adopted. The original, strictly centralist proposal envisaged only an act on the CSAS, which would eventually set forth a specific status for the SAS.⁴¹ The centralisation process that commenced in late 1959 ended four years later in a significantly different political and social situation of belated destalinisation. The fact that the Slovak Academy was granted its own law and retained its own members and institutes largely called into question the degree of its absorption by the CSAS that had initially been assumed. The development plan of the Czechoslovak Academy for 1963–1970 proposed accelerating

38 He mentioned the chairman of the Ideological Commission of the CC CPC, Vladimír Koucký.

39 A SAS, f. RO SAV, box 8, Minutes of the 26th General Assembly of the SAS, 10 April 1968, Discussion paper by Miloš Gosiorovský.

40 ŠMIDÁK, Miroslav. *Institucionální vývoj Československé akademie věd v letech 1968–1969 očima jednoho z přímých aktérů*. Praha: Masarykův ústav a Archiv AV ČR, 2011, p. 31 (hereafter: ŠMIDÁK, M. *Institucionální vývoj*).

41 See: FRANC, Martin. *Ivan Málek a vědní politika 1952–1989 aneb Jediný opravdový komunista?*. Praha: Masarykův ústav a Archiv AV ČR, 2010, p. 173.

the growth of the SAS as part of the equalisation of the imbalance between the Czech and Slovak parts of the state.⁴²

In the end, the academies chose what was advantageous from the new laws.⁴³ The close cooperation between the academies manifested itself in the coordinated defence of their common interests. The disadvantageous reform of the social science institutes, ordered by the government in 1964, was sabotaged by the leaderships of the CSAS and SAS by not implementing it. An unintended consequence of the closer association of the SAS with the CSAS was the expansion and strengthening of liberalising trends within the Slovak academic community. Indeed, it was in the mid-1960s that closer institutional and personal cooperation was established between the various social science institutes in the Czech lands and Slovakia.⁴⁴ In the 1960s, the Presidium of the Slovak Academy of Sciences showed support for the efforts of the CSAS Presidium “to take a more prominent role in the preparation of critical scientific analyses of the current problems of our economic and social life, so that they could become the basis for the managing work of the leading state and party bodies”.⁴⁵ This was a manifestation of the growing self-confidence of the academic community and its ambition to raise political topics.

Failed Attempt at Federalisation

In the late 1960s, the ideas of democratisation of society, greater tolerance of opinion, the elimination of bureaucratism and freedom of scientific work found enormous support among the academic elites. Academicians were among the strong supporters of the Prague Spring reforms. As early as February 1968, a delegation from the CSAS met with the new First Secretary of the CC CPC, Alexander Dubček,⁴⁶ declaring their support for the reform policy of the new leadership of the CPC and offering their help in its elaboration.

Unlike in the Czech environment, however, in Slovakia the struggle against the legacy of Stalinism had not only democratising but also nationalistic

42 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 43, 152nd Meeting of the Presidium of the SAS, 8 April 1963.

43 The fact that the SAS became part of the CSAS ensured the equality of salaries. Previously, the SAS employees earned less.

44 KAMENCOVÁ, Lýdia. Vzostup a pád spoločenských vied na Slovensku v rokoch 1963–1970. In SVOBODNÝ, Petr, ZILYNSKÁ, Blanka (eds.). *Česká věda a Pražské jaro (1963–1970). Sborník z konference (Praha 22.–23. listopadu 2000)*. Praha: Karolinum, 2001, p. 196.

45 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 7, 20th General Assembly of the SAS, 10 April 1964.

46 It also included the highest officials of the SAS, Štefan Schwarz, Dionýz Blaškovič, Vojtech Kellö and Emil Špaldon. See: HUDEK, A. *Slovenská akadémia vied v “obrodnom procese”*, p. 146.

overtones. The majority of Slovak intellectual elites considered the 1950s as an era of violent suppression of Slovak national emancipation. In the Slovak environment, the issue of Czech-Slovak relations became a principal theme of the reform movement, with the federalisation of the state being the key element of the Slovak reform programme. As early as the beginning of March 1968, a meeting was held at the conference centre of the Slovak Academy of Sciences in Smolenice Castle, which is considered one of the triggers of the federalisation of the state.⁴⁷ Formally, it was to be a meeting of an interdisciplinary team on the topic of “Development of the political system in a socialist society.” However, the discussion of Czech and Slovak experts soon focused on the question of the constitutional organisation of the Czechoslovak state.

The question of Slovak emancipation also arose in discussions on the relations between the Czechoslovak and Slovak academies. The expectations of Slovak scientists were voiced at the 26th General Assembly of the Slovak Academy of Sciences held on 10 April 1968. The chairman of the SAS, mathematician Štefan Schwarz, reminded those present that the Academy had experienced “unfortunate and explicitly forced interventions of an organisational nature” in the past.⁴⁸ Among the main negatives, he listed the attempted absorption of the SAS by the CSAS. This statement opened the door to further criticisms. Michal Pecho, a representative of the CC CPS, assured those present that all the previous distortions were the fault of the “Prague Centre”,⁴⁹ which had blocked the efforts of the CPS leadership to achieve Slovak equality. Academic officials who had participated in the centralisation process in the early 1960s also defended themselves in a similar way.

Other speakers accused CSAS officials of sabotaging the development of the SAS institutes and attempting to turn them into mere service centres for the Prague-based institutes.⁵⁰ Strong criticism, especially from representatives of the social sciences, was levelled at CSAS chairman František Šorm. There were also calls for his resignation, along with other members of the CSAS and SAS who had allegedly worked to the detriment of Slovak science.

Understandably, the Slovak academic community associated with the SAS perceived the centralising changes in a significantly negative light. However, this was not primarily due to the actual changes, which were not too radical,

47 ŽATKULIAK, Jozef. Otvorenie problematiky federalizácie štátu roku 1968. In LONDÁK, Miroslav et al. *Rok 1968: eto Vaše delo*. Bratislava: Historický ústav SAV, 2008, p. 40.

48 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 8, Minutes of the 26th General Assembly of the SAS, 10 April 1968, Introductory speech by the President of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Štefan Schwarz.

49 Ibid., Discussion paper by Michal Pecho.

50 Ibid., Discussion paper by Dimitrij Andrusov.

as the SAS staff eventually admitted. The symbolic meaning of the SAS's subordinate position to the CSAS played a crucial role here, mainly because the CSAS was perceived as a Czech and not a statewide academy in the Slovak environment. In this respect, the formulation that the forthcoming Action Programme of the SAS should consider the relations "to the CSAS, i.e., to Czech science"⁵¹ is telling.

Therefore, calls were coming from the Slovak side to urgently define the new relations between the academies in legal terms, based on the federative principle. As pointed out by Š. Schwarz: "We are in favour of a fully democratic and symmetrical constitutional model. This naturally has consequences for the organisational relations between the CSAS and the SAS."⁵² The SAS Presidium requested that a working group be set up which, in cooperation with the CSAS Presidium, would examine the relations between the two academies and propose measures to eliminate the negative elements in their functioning.⁵³ The working group was to submit a proposal for a legislative arrangement between the SAS and the CSAS to the academic bodies for public discussion on 30 September 1968.

Plans for the reorganisation of academic research within the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic envisaged from the outset the existence of three academies – two national and one, derivative, federal academy. A separate law was to be drawn up for each of them. Within the SAS, the desire for the greatest possible autonomy and independence of the national academies, with the weakest possible status of the federal institution, prevailed. All cooperation was to be left on an entirely voluntary basis, without the establishment of a special coordinating body. The emphasis on equality and independence of the future national academies was much more apparent in the Slovak environment than in the Czech. The reason for this was the differing experience with centralisation measures.

The Czech-Slovak debates on the powers of the academies thus replicated those on the federalisation of the state. The Slovak side preferred strong, autonomous national components, while the Czech side favoured more dominant federal institutions. The representatives of the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences argued that it was in the interest of science not to abandon the unified state plan of research. F. Šorm admitted that the federative transformation and the application of so-called socialist democracy created the need for a change in the management of Czechoslovak science. However, he argued that it was

51 Ibid., Resolutions.

52 Ibid., Introductory speech by the President of the SAS, Štefan Schwarz.

53 Ibid., Resolutions.

necessary to preserve the positive elements of the former system, especially the preparation of binding long-term research plans.⁵⁴ The Secretariat of the CSAS Presidium therefore proposed the establishment of a “voluntary coordination group”⁵⁵ for the organisation of research in Czechoslovakia.⁵⁶

Significantly, Šorm’s proposal was unequivocally and unanimously rejected by the SAS Presidium. Its members disagreed with the establishment of the coordination group because they considered it “a power body superior to the national scientific research areas”.⁵⁷ They were also negative about the existence of a unified statewide research plan because “national institutions would thus lose their sovereign right to draw up their own plans and submit them to national governments.”⁵⁸ The primary desire of most SAS representatives was to move as far away as possible from all forms of governance of science and research of the “Novotný era”. The result was a reluctance to support any proposal that tended to limit the sovereignty of the national academies.

The increasingly strong emphasis on the direction of the Slovak debate towards the constitutional and national question caused a growing differentiation between the Slovak and Czech academic communities. One example is the fate of the manifesto entitled “Two Thousand Words”,⁵⁹ written in Prague in June 1968. While in the Czech lands the appeal aroused extraordinary interest and gained many signatories, it was almost completely ignored or outright rejected in Slovakia. One of the main reasons for this was probably that it did not deal with the problem of Czech-Slovak relations.

Because of the aforementioned disputes, the drafting of the final version of the laws on academies was constantly delayed. The original approval dates, scheduled for March 1969, proved illusory, not only because of the invasion by the Warsaw Pact troops. The final agreement on the federalisation of Czechoslovakia⁶⁰ brought changes to the Slovak Academy of Sciences even without the new law. As of 1 January 1969, the SAS became a first-level budget organisation and was thus directly linked to the budget of the Slovak Socialist Re-

54 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 66, 250th Meeting of the Presidium of the SAS, 17 February 1969.

55 It was to comprise the President of the CSAS, the Federal Minister of Planning, the Ministers of Technical and Investment Development, the Ministers of national governments, and prominent representatives of Czechoslovak science.

56 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 66, 250th Meeting of the Presidium of the SAS, 17 February 1969.

57 Ibid.

58 Ibid.

59 The impulse for the publication of the document, which called for the democratisation process to be accelerated, came from prominent Czech natural scientists (Jan Brod, Jaroslav Poupa, Otto Wichterle, Bohumil Sekla).

60 The only reform that survived 21 August 1968.

public (hereafter: SSR). From the beginning of 1969, the last CSAS institute in Slovakia, the Institute of Virology, was incorporated into the SAS.⁶¹ From then on, the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences only had institutes in the Czech part of the republic.

The SAS and the CSAS approved drafts of three new laws in mid-May 1969 and submitted them to the legislative process. However, it was already too late. The documents stressing the self-governing principle and the freedom of science directly opposed the plans of the normalising party leadership. Following the direct intervention by the CC CPC, they were shelved *ad acta* in the autumn of 1969.⁶² At the same time, the preparation of amendments to the existing laws began.

The amendment to the Act on the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences was adopted in an accelerated procedure in the form of a statutory measure of the Presidium of the Federal Assembly⁶³ on 19 March 1970, while the Slovak National Council approved a similar statutory norm on 28 April 1970. Both amendments were made on the same foundations and for the same purpose. In the short term, they were intended to clear the way for the intended “consolidation steps”; in the long term, they allowed for direct and complete control of the functioning of the SAS and the CSAS by the state and, in particular, by the party authorities.

Both documents were based on the premise of the unity of Czechoslovak science. The asymmetrical model of 1963 remained in force. The official explanation was that “in view of the role of science in the development of the Czechoslovak national economy and society, as well as the need for its central management, the previous position of the CSAS [...] and, in principle, the relationship between the CSAS and the SAS were maintained, but the position of the SAS as the highest national and regional scientific institution was strengthened, and the SAS became institutionally independent.”⁶⁴ The Slovak Academy formally remained an organic part of the CSAS, but in reality it was linked to the CSAS much less than before. Only in the area of organisation of foreign relations did the dependence remain.

61 A SAS, Coll. RO SAV, box 65, 247th Meeting of the Presidium of the SAS, 18 December 1968, Report on the proposal for the preparation of the economic, financial and administrative independence of the SAS as of 1 January 1969.

62 TIBENSKÝ, Ján. *Inštitucionálny vývin SAV a výstavba jej pracovísk*. In IDEM. (ed.). *Z dejín vied a techniky na Slovensku.*, 9. Bratislava: Veda, 1979, p. 24 (hereafter: TIBENSKÝ, J. *Inštitucionálny vývin SAV*).

63 MÍŠKOVÁ, A., BARVÍKOVÁ, H., ŠMIDÁK, M. *Československá akademie věd*, p. 54.

64 TIBENSKÝ, J. *Inštitucionálny vývin SAV*, p. 24.

In practical matters of its functioning and financing, the SAS no longer had to turn to the CSAS, but to the government of the SSR, to which it was accountable for its activities. Mutual links remained in fact only in the field of scientific cooperation on statewide or international projects. From the point of view of the SAS, the CSAS had in many respects turned into a Czech national academy. However, as Miroslav Šmidák wrote: “The effort to gain full equality of Slovak science in the common state was thus ‘rewarded’ with cynical humour only by the fact that the Slovaks had to finance their academy of sciences themselves from 1970 onwards, whereas the CSAS (which was now made up solely of Czech institutes) continued to be financed from the federal budget.”⁶⁵ This arrangement, with minor changes, lasted until the fall of the communist regime.

Conclusion

The Slovak Academy of Sciences, like its predecessors, from its inception built an image of a national institution that resisted pressures from the “Prague centre” and protected the Slovak intellectual and academic elite. The Slovak academic community, as well as some Slovak communists, perceived its functioning through a national lens as one of the symbols of the equal status of Czechs and Slovaks. Even among Slovak scientists, who had reservations about the introduction of the Soviet model of the organisation of science and research, the attitude towards the “national” SAS was much more positive than towards the statewide CSAS, which was, moreover, perceived more as a Czech institution. This fact to a large extent defined the views in the Slovak environment on the relations between the CSAS and the SAS.

Even before the establishment of the SAS, the prevailing opinion among Slovak academic elites was that there was a need for the greatest possible degree of autonomy from the central academy. This conviction shaped the activities of SAS representatives in the following decades. Based on the current political situation, only the manner in which the representatives of the Slovak Academy promoted their goal or at least defended the existing situation varied.

The centralising measures of the early 1960s, which almost led to the demise of the SAS and its dissolution into the CSAS, also served as a warning to loyal party members in the Slovak academic community that in the reality of a centralised Czechoslovakia, the very existence of the national academy was in constant danger. This feeling defined the attitudes of the Slovak academic

65 ŠMIDÁK, M. *Institucionální vývoj*, p. 187.

community during the Prague Spring. It influenced the process of drafting new laws to ensure a new, federal organisation of the academies of sciences. However, differing ideas on the Slovak and Czech sides contributed significantly to the fact that the prepared drafts could not be approved. Instead, the 1970 normalisation amendment to the Act on CSAS subsequently defined the relationship between the two academies until the fall of the communist regime. This move also brought to a close the activities of the leadership of both the SAS and the CSAS in the area of defining their mutual relations. The normalisation policy deadened all such efforts.

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Andrej Sirácky se Štefanem Schwarzem na XII. valném shromáždění ČSAV 17. listopadu 1960; foto: Jiří Plechatý (MÚA, A AV ČR, f. Reportáže ČSAV a AV ČR, sign. FOP 334, č. 12)

Předseda ČSAV, akademik František Šorm (vlevo) s Andrejem Siráckym na XVI. valném shromáždění ČSAV, které se konalo 16. a 17. listopadu 1962; foto: Jiří Plechatý (MÚA, A AV ČR, f. Reportáže ČSAV a AV ČR, sign. FOP 524, č. 33)